

become too tall and prone to lodging. This type is best suited to conditions where the water depth is great and the water rise rate is rapid. However, even under deepwater conditions, the plant parts above the water level are too long

and the plants tend to lodge.

Type B is probably the optimum response for deep water. Even at medium-deepwater level, plants with type B reaction perform better because they are shorter than plants with type A.

Type C or intermediate height varieties with very limited elongation ability are possible for medium-deep water. Such plants, however, will not give reasonable yields in deeper water, even with the addition of N. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Cold-tolerant varieties from China

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Eleven best varieties based on cold tolerance at 4 growth stages have been selected from 1,474 Chinese varieties in the IRRI germplasm bank. The methods used for testing at the different growth stages were described in earlier papers. Early seedling stage was tested at 5°C, seedling stage at 12°C, panicle development stage and flowering stage at 15°C.

All entries (see table) are sinica except Hung Chao Lu Yu and Ai Yeh Lu. Ai Yeh Lu has short growth duration and Hung Chao Lu Yu has high protein content (13.1 to 13.6%). The agronomic characteristics of sinica varieties selected

Varieties cold tolerant at 4 stages.

Acc. no.	Variety	Cold tolerance score ^a			
		ES	SS	PD	FS
01178	Chiang Tsenf Tao Ju	1	3	2	1
01179	Hung Chao Lu Yu	1	3	3	2
01254	Y Chang Ju	1	3	3	3
01269	Ta Chang Kong	3	2	2	3
01385	Fang Chi	3	3	2	3
01395	Chu Cheng	3	3	3	3
07288	Fi-Lai-Feng	1	2	3	3
10360	Ai-Yeh Lu (PI 160965)	3	3	2	2
28474	Hsiung-Yo 613	3	2	2	3
36852	Ching-Hsi 15	1	3	2	3
36853	Ching-Hsi 17	1	2	2	3

^a ES = early seedling stage, SS = seedling stage, PD = panicle development, FS = flowering stage. 1 = good, 9 = poor.

do not differ greatly. Fi-Lai-Feng has a long maturity period, but is resistant to bacterial blight. Chu Cheng has the highest 1,000-grain weight.

Most of these donor varieties do not have disease and insect resistance.

Crosses with varieties resistant to diseases and insect pests and with good plant type are necessary to improve grain yield and general adaptability. Seeds for national breeding programs are available at IRRI. ■

Evaluation of rooting ability of rice in puddled soil in low temperature

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In areas where temperature is low during transplanting, recovery of rice varieties after transplanting is poor because of poor rooting ability. To develop a practical and efficient method of screening varieties for good rooting ability, entries in the 1980 International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery were evaluated 23 days after transplanting at Banaue, Philippines, and 13 days after transplanting at Chuncheon, Korea. There were 245 entries at Banaue and 215 at Chuncheon. High-tillering and vigorous varieties were given a visual

Correlation coefficients among plant characters at Banaue, Philippines, and Chuncheon, Korea.